

The Profile of Serum Calcium Levels in Pediatric Chronic Kidney Disease in West Java

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Abstract

Background: Calcium metabolism disorders often occur in patients with CKD. Research discussing the topic of calcium levels in children with CKD is still limited. **Objective:** To determine the description of serum calcium levels in pediatric patients with CKD and to determine the relationship between characteristics such as age, gender, etiology, and stage of CKD with serum calcium levels in pediatric patients with CKD at Dr. Hasan Sadikin General Hospital. **Method:** A cross-sectional study of pediatric patients with CKD in the inpatient ward of Dr. Hasan Sadikin General Hospital, Bandung, from January 2020 to December 2022. Inclusion criteria were patient records of pediatric patients with CKD aged 3 months - 17 years, with exclusion criteria of incomplete medical records of pediatric patients with CKD and those experiencing acute exacerbation. Serum calcium levels were obtained from medical records. Data were processed using SPSS version 26. **Results:** During the 3-year period, 169 research subjects met the criteria. The age of the patients was mostly in the range of 13-17 years and female patients dominated by 52.7%. It was found that in children with CKD, the highest proportion of etiology was nephrotic syndrome (53.3%) and the highest stage was stage 5 (54.4%). The median serum calcium level of all pediatric patients with CKD was 4.85 mg/dL. There was a significant relationship between gender, etiology and stage of CKD on serum calcium levels of pediatric patients with CKD. **Conclusion:** Serum calcium levels in most pediatric patients with CKD at Dr. Hasan Sadikin General Hospital, Bandung were still within normal limits.

Keywords: *serum calcium, chronic kidney disease, children.*

Suggested citation: Widiasta, A., Milwan, G.A., & Hafsa, T. (2025). The Profile of Serum Calcium Levels in Pediatric Chronic Kidney Disease in West Java. *Scientia. Technology, Science and Society*, 2(5), 109-117. DOI: 10.59324/stss.2025.2(5).09

Introduction

Chronic kidney disease is a public health problem with increasing incidence and prevalence globally (Dorgelo & Oostrom, 2022; Xie et al., 2018; Ghimirey, et al., 2013). Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is damage to the structure or function of the kidneys, or a decrease in the glomerular filtration rate

<60 mL/min/1.73 m² for more than 3 months (Rovin et al., 2021). From the 2017 Global Burden of Disease study, there was an increase in the prevalence of CKD sufferers of all ages by 29.3% (from 26.4% to 32.6%) from 1990 to 2017, and an increase in the global CKD mortality rate of 41.5% from 1990 to 2017 (Bikbov et al., 2020). Based on the 2018 Basic Health Research (Riskesdas) data, the prevalence of the population ≥ 15 years in Indonesia who suffer from chronic kidney disease is 0.38%.

CKD in children, as well as in adults, is associated with severe consequences, including increased risk of mortality, renal failure, cardiovascular disease, bone mineral disorders, and malnutrition (Ahn Yo Han Kang Hee Gyung, 2021). Mineral and bone disorders in CKD or CKD mineral and bone disorder (CKD-MBD) can be characterized by disturbances in the metabolism of calcium, phosphate, parathyroid hormone, calcitriol (1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D or 1,25D), and fibroblast growth factor 23 (FGF23). In CKD patients, serum 1,25D is decreased due to the effect of FGF23 which suppresses the conversion of 25D to 1,25D through inhibition of the enzyme 1- α -hydroxylase⁷. Thus, patients with CKD are at risk of decreased calcium absorption due to decreased levels of 1,25D and active calcium transport (Perwad et al., 2007). Hypocalcemia (due to decreased intestinal calcium absorption mediated by decreased levels of 1,25D) contributes to the development of secondary hyperparathyroidism and renal osteodystrophy. From the study in hemodialysis patients, it was found that there is a relationship between hypocalcemia and the risk of mortality (Floege et al., 2011). In children with CKD, CKD-MBD can cause bone deformities, bone pain, growth retardation, and one of the most important is uremic vascular calcification. Uremic vascular calcification is an important cause of long-term morbidity and mortality (Oh et al., 2002).

The risk of mineral and bone disorders is one of the important reasons for the management of pediatric patients with CKD through the administration of calcium and phosphorus. To provide this management, it is necessary to check the calcium and phosphorus levels of pediatric patients with CKD regularly, especially in CKD stages 2-5 (McAlister et al., 2020). In addition, checking the levels of calcium, phosphorus, alkaline phosphatase, parathormone (PTH), and 1,25D levels is important to monitor the presence of CKD-MBD complications in pediatric patients with CKD (Bakkaloglu et al., 2021). Research by Lou et al. states that comprehensive monitoring and management of serum calcium, phosphate, and PTH levels can improve the quality of life of CKD patients receiving dialysis (Luo & Chen, 2020). Research discussing the topic of calcium levels in children with CKD is still limited. In a study conducted by Ziółkowska et al on 37 children with CKD stages 3 – 5 with an age range of 1.6-17 years, serum calcium was still within normal limits (Ziółkowska et al., 2014). In another study by Lestari et al on 28 children with CKD, 3 subjects with stages 1 – 2 and 12 subjects with stages 3 – 5 experienced hypocalcemia (Lestari et al., 2020). There were differences in the findings of existing studies regarding calcium levels in children with CKD. The purpose of this study was to determine serum calcium levels in pediatric patients with chronic kidney disease and to determine the relationship between characteristics such as age, gender, etiology, and CKD stage with serum calcium levels in pediatric patients with CKD at Dr. Hasan Sadikin General Hospital, Bandung.

Methods

This research is a study with a cross-sectional design, using secondary data in the form of medical records at RSUP Dr. Hasan Sadikin Bandung from January 2020 to December 2022. Data collection was carried out after obtaining ethical exemption from the Research Ethics Committee of Padjadjaran University Bandung No: 1387/UN6.KEP/EC/2022, and from the RSHS Health Research Ethics Committee No: 1030/UN6.KEP/EC/2021. The research population was all

medical record data of pediatric patients with CKD who were hospitalized at the Children's Nephrology Polyclinic at RSUP Dr. Hasan Sadikin Bandung. The research subjects were medical record data from pediatric patients with CKD aged 3 months – 17 years for the period 1 January 2020 – 31 December 2022. Medical record data from patients who were repeatedly hospitalized (readmission) remained included in the study. Research sampling was carried out using total sampling. Exclusion criteria were medical record data from pediatric patients with CKD who experienced acute exacerbations and medical record data that did not have data on calcium ion levels and CKD stage.

Data on age, gender, CKD etiology, CKD stage, serum calcium levels, treatment, and complications of pediatric patients with CKD were obtained from medical record data. The etiology of CKD is classified into nephrotic syndrome, glomerulonephritis, CAKUT (Congenital Anomalies of Kidney and Urinary Tract), HUS (haemolytic uraemic syndrome), lupus nephritis, and others. The CKD stage is obtained from the estimated glomerular filtration rate (GFR) which is calculated using the Schwartz formula and grouped into stages 1-2 and stages 3-5. Data on serum calcium levels are ionized calcium levels (mg/dL). Treatment data for pediatric patients with CKD are grouped into immunosuppressants, calcium supplementation, vitamin D supplementation, and dialysis. Data on complications experienced by patients is classified into hypertension, anemia, bone disease, short stature, hypoalbuminemia, hyponatremia, and hyperkalemia.

Characteristic data is presented in the form of numbers and percentages. Serum calcium level data was tested for data distribution using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test because the sample size was more than 50 and it was found that the distribution of serum calcium level data was not normal so the data was presented in median (min-max) form. The data obtained was processed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 and displayed in table form.

Results

There are 202 medical records of pediatric patients with CKD who were hospitalized at RSUP Dr. Hasan Sadikin Bandung for the period 1 January 2020 - 31 December 2022. A total of 33 medical record data of pediatric patients with CKD were excluded because they were experiencing an acute exacerbation, incomplete stage data, or incomplete calcium level data, so that 169 patient medical record data were subjects in this study. The characteristics of pediatric patients with CKD are presented in Table 1. Based on gender, 80 (47.3%) research subjects were male and 89 (52.7%) female. The largest age group of pediatric patients with CKD is 13-17 years (55%), the most common etiology is nephrotic syndrome (53.3%), and the most common stage is stage 3-5 (65.7%). Research subjects can have more than one category of treatment given and complications experienced. The most common treatment given to pediatric patients with CKD is calcium supplementation (63.6%). The most common complication experienced by pediatric patients with CKD was hypertension (41.4%).

Table 1. Subject Characteristic

Characteristics	Total (n=169)	
	n	%
Age		
3 – 5 months		
6 – 12 months		
1 – 5 years	18	10.7
6 – 12 years	58	34.3
13 – 18 years	93	55

Gender		
Male	80	47.3
Female	89	52.7
Causes of CKD		
NS	90	53.3
Glomerulonephritis	14	8.3
CAKUT	10	5.9
HUS	2	1.2
Lupus nephritis	18	10.7
Miscellaneous	35	20.7
Stage of CKD		
G1 – 2	58	34.3
G3 – 5	111	65.7
Treatment		
Immunosuppressant	97	57.4
Calcium carbonate	107	63.3
Vitamin D	106	62.7
Dialysis	57	33.7
Complication		
Hypertension	70	41.4
Anemia	36	21.3
MBD	1	0.6
Short stature	33	19.5
Hypoalbuminea	21	12.4
Hyponatremia	8	4.7
Hyperkalemia	6	3.6

Data on serum calcium levels of pediatric patients with CKD are presented in Table 2. The median serum calcium level of all pediatric patients with CKD was 4.85 mg/dL, where the lowest calcium level was 1.25 mg/dL and the highest calcium level was 7.37 mg/dL.

Table 2. Calcium Serum Levels in Chronic Kidney Disease Children

Variable	Total (n=169)
Calcium serum levels mg/dL (median, min-max)	4.85(1.25-7.37)

Serum calcium levels of pediatric patients with CKD based on age, gender, etiology and CKD stage are presented in Table 3. The highest median serum calcium levels were found in the 1 – 5 year age group (5.03 mg/dL). Median serum calcium levels in women were higher than men (4.97 vs 4.72 mg/dL). Based on the etiology of CKD, the highest median serum calcium level was found in the etiology of lupus nephritis (5.12 mg/dL). Based on CKD stage, the median serum calcium level in stages 1 – 2 is higher than stages 3-5 (4.96 vs 4.66 mg/dL). Based on analysis using the Mann Whitney test, differences in gender and CKD stage had a significant relationship with serum calcium levels. Based on analysis using the Kruskal-Wallis test, CKD etiology has a significant relationship with serum calcium levels. Age did not have a significant relationship with serum calcium levels.

Table 3. Correlation between Age, Gender, Etiology, and Stage of the Disease

Category	Calcium Serum Levels (n=169) (kalsium ion mg/dL)	P value
Age group		
3 – 5 Months	-	0,15 ^a
6 – 12 months	-	
1 – 5 years	5.03(2.61-7.37)	
6 – 12 years	4.94(1.25-6.84)	
13 – 18 years	4.73(2.77-7.15)	
Male		
Male	4.72 (3.09-7.15)	0,01 ^b
Female	4.97 (1.25-7.37)	
Chronic kidney disease		
NS	4.94(3.40-7.37)	0,00 ^a
Glomerulonephritis	4.78(2.77-6.22)	
CAKUT	4.75(3.09-6.06)	
HUS	4.17(4.00-4.33)	
Lupus nephritis	5.12(4.53-6.84)	
Miscelanous	4.49(1.25-5.97)	
CKD stage		
G1 – 2	4.96 (3.40-6.02)	0,03 ^b
G3 – 5	4.66 (1.25-7.37)	

Note: ^aUji Kruskal-Wallis; ^bUji Mann-Whitney; CKD, chronic kidney disease; NS, nephrotic syndrome; HUS, hemolytic uremic syndrome; CAKUT, congenital anomaly of the kidney and urinary tract

Discussion

In this study, serum calcium levels of pediatric patients with CKD who were hospitalized at the Children's Nephrology Polyclinic at Dr. RSUP. Hasan Sadikin Bandung for the period 1 January 2020 – 31 December 2022 is still within normal limits based on references to normal serum calcium levels from the clinical laboratory of RSUP Dr. Hasan Sadikin is 4.5-5.6 mg/dL. Overall, median relative serum calcium levels decreased with increasing CKD stage.

The dominant age in this study was 13-17 years, different from previous research where the dominant age in the study was 6-11 years (Lestari et al., 2020). In this study, the proportion of women (52.7%) was higher than men (47.3%). The results of these characteristics are not in line with previous studies in Indonesia and Lithuania where men were more dominant than women (Lestari et al., 2020; Masalskienė et al., 2021). This is possibly because this study used medical record data of patients who were repeatedly hospitalized (readmission). Several causes of CKD in this study include nephrotic syndrome (SN) (53.3%) which consists of primary and secondary nephrotic syndrome, minimal and non-minimal nephrotic syndrome, and steroid resistant nephrotic syndrome (SNRS); glomerulonephritis (8.3%) consisting of rapidly progressive glomerulonephritis (RPGN) and membranoproliferative glomerulonephritis (MPGN); congenital anomalies of kidney and urinary tract (CAKUT) (5.9%) consisting of bilateral hydronephrosis and vesicoureteral reflux (VUR) (Geary, & Schaefer, 2016); haemolytic uraemic syndrome (HUS) (1.2%); Lupus nephritis (10.7%); and others (20.7%) consisting of polycystic kidney disease, Alport syndrome, neurogenic bladder, focal segmental glomerulosclerosis (FSGS), and incomplete medical record etiology data.

The dominant etiology of CKD in this study was nephrotic syndrome. In line with previous studies in Indonesia which stated that the etiology of the majority of pediatric patients with CKD was SNRS (Lestari et al., 2020; Widiasta et al., 2017). From research at RSUP Dr. Hasan Sadikin

Bandung and RSUP Dr. M. Djamil Padang found that most pediatric patients with CKD were at stage 1 (Sani et al., 2022; Widiasta et al., 2017, 2025). The largest proportion of CKD in this study was stage 5 (54.4%). This could be caused by medical record data from stage 5 CKD patients who were repeatedly hospitalized (readmission) or because the research was conducted at RSUP Dr. Hasan Sadikin Bandung is a referral hospital/central general hospital so patients tend to be CKD patients with advanced stages. The most common treatment in this study was calcium supplementation. This is in accordance with previous research in Indonesia by Lestari et al that the most common treatment for pediatric patients with CKD was calcium supplementation (Lestari et al., 2020). The most common complication in this study was hypertension (41.4%). The next complications were anemia in 36 subjects (21.3%) and short stature in 33 subjects (19.5%).

The research results listed in Table 2 show that the median serum calcium level of all pediatric patients with CKD 4.85 mg/dL is still within the normal limit of calcium ion levels. The lowest calcium level value was 1.25 mg/dL and the highest calcium level was 7.37 mg/dL. It was found that several pediatric patients with CKD had calcium metabolism disorders.

Serum calcium levels in pediatric patients with CKD decreased as the patient's age group increased. Median serum calcium levels based on age have the highest median calcium levels in the 1-5 year age group, and the median value decreases as the age group increases. This can occur due to age-dependent calcium physiology, where there is a decrease in serum calcium concentration during early childhood growth and puberty so that calcium levels decrease with age (Liu et al., 2012; Loh & Metz, 2015; Marwaha et al., 2010). In this study, the median serum calcium level in women (4.97 mg/dL) was higher than the median serum calcium level in men (4.72 mg/dL). From the test results of this research, it was found that there was a significant relationship between gender and serum calcium levels in pediatric patients with CKD. Previous research on healthy children in China showed that boys' calcium levels were significantly higher than girls', while research in India²⁰ found total calcium levels were significantly higher in boys than girls but ionized calcium levels did not show a significant difference (Liu et al., 2012). Differences in the results of this study and previous research may occur due to differences in the subjects studied, where previous research was conducted on healthy children, this research was conducted on children with CKD. Other factors that can influence are socio-demographic factors and using medical record data of patients who are repeatedly hospitalized (readmission). Based on the etiology of CKD, the highest median serum calcium level was in the etiology of lupus nephritis (5.12 mg/dL) and the lowest was in the etiology of HUS (4.17 mg/dL). There is a significant relationship between the etiology of CKD and the serum calcium levels of pediatric patients with CKD. Median serum calcium levels based on CKD stage decreased as the CKD stage group increased. Based on analysis using the Mann Whitney test, stages 1 – 2 and stages 3 – 5 CKD have a significant relationship with serum calcium levels in pediatric patients with CKD. The results of this study are supported by previous research in Indonesia which found that the number of subjects with low calcium levels (hypocalcemia) was greater in CKD stages 3-5 than in stages 1-2 (Lestari et al., 2020).

By knowing serum calcium levels, appropriate management can be carried out for pediatric patients with CKD to avoid complications such as impaired growth and vascular calcification, improve the patient's quality of life, and reduce mortality rates. The limitation of this study is that it uses medical record data from CKD patients who have been re-hospitalized, so data on the characteristics of the same patient can be calculated more than once. Another limitation is that CKD treatment data is not included in the laboratory results of calcium levels, so it is not possible to know whether the calcium levels obtained in the study have been affected by treatment or not.

Conclusion

From the results of this study, serum calcium levels were obtained in the majority of pediatric patients with CKD at Dr. RSUP. Hasan Sadikin is still within normal limits. There is a significant relationship between gender, etiology and stage of CKD on serum calcium levels in pediatric patients with CKD. Research that can be carried out next is in the form of analytical research on factors that can influence calcium levels, such as food intake or medication.

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